

CHEMISTRY

STRUCTURAL-GROUP CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME SOFTENERS BY HIGH RESOLUTION ^{13}C NMR SPECTROSCOPY

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Abstract

A pilot study of softeners Norman 346 and Norman 132 including their synthetic plant analogues Phytonorman 212 and Phytonorman 213 with an ultra-low content of carcinogens were carried out by ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. Studied objects Norman 346 and Norman 132 are used as softeners for synthetic rubbers, tires and rubber products. Phytonorman 212 and Phytonorman 213 oils are their synthetic plant analogues obtained from a renewable vegetable raw material – wood. The studied samples are environmentally safe products with a reduced content of carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and provide the best car tire grip on wet surfaces, rolling resistance and wear resistance. Molar fractions of major hydrocarbon groups and aromatic carbons of ring groups of studied softeners according to ^{13}C NMR spectra were determined. Answer to the question about the effectiveness of the use of one of the studied softener in comparison with others was obtained.

Keywords: ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy; process oil; synthetic analogues of vegetable oils; functional group; qualitative analysis; quantitative composition; aromaticity.

1. Introduction

Intensive development of the rubber industry, increase in output of existing and creation of new types of rubber requires constant improvement raw material base. Proper selection and introduction of softeners into the rubber mixture allow not only directionally adjust finished product properties and improve processing of polymer compositions, but also to change adhesiveness, cohesive strength, vulcanization parameters, increase service life and weather resistance products, improve adhesive bond with reinforcing materials [1, 72-78]. Modern industry dictates stringent requirements to tire products, primarily to reduce fuel losses associated with rolling resistance tires. It is known that one of the ways to improve histological resistance properties of rubbers is a decrease in the number of free bare ends of macromolecular chains, because end sections of macromolecules form an inactive part vulcanization mesh. For non-functionalized rubbers, this is achieved by increasing the molecular mass or narrowing of the molecular weight distribution polymer. Decreased polydispersity index of kauchuka requires solving many technological problems. Therefore, the simplest is to obtain a polymer with high Mooney viscosity. At the same time, such polymers are characterized by an increased level of viscosity rubber compound, which can create difficulties in processing, as well as the associated increased energy consumption in the process of preparing rubber compounds based on it. To improve the processability of rubbers, many studies and experiments on their physical modification and determination of the influence of various types of filling threads on the technological properties of rubbers ([2, 20-24]; [3, 13-15]; [4, 134-139]; [5, 40-43]; [6, 222-227]). One of the main

methods of structural modification of the polymers is plasticization, i.e., the introduction into the polymer of personal low molecular weight substances - plasticizers. With the introduction of plasticizers, the viscosity of rubbers, their processing is facilitated, the elasticity and frost resistance of the material are improved.

NMR spectroscopy can be used to study various softeners, expanding the possibilities for research in the field of geological and chemical problems ([7]; [8]; [9, 6942-6946]; [10, 1-9]; [11, 2858-2864]; [12, 117622]; [13, 597-598]). The objective of this work is to explore the possibilities of using new softeners – Norman 346, Norman 132 and their synthetic plant analogues Phytonorman 212, Phytonorman 213, respectively, by ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. The studied softener samples are produced by the Orgkhim company as part of a rubber mixture intended for the manufacture of treads for automobile radial tires. A comparative analysis of the structural-group characteristics of the studied softeners obtained by analyzing the ^{13}C NMR spectra similar to that carried out earlier in previous studies on the study of the structural-group characteristics of oil samples was carried out ([14, 12-18]; [15, 256-262]; [16, 995]; [17, 269-274]; [18, 7-11]). Based on the results of the study, the answer to the question about the effectiveness of the use of one of the studied softener in comparison with others was obtained.

2. Materials and methods

NMR experiments on studied oil samples were performed on a Bruker Avance III HD 700 NMR spectrometer. The studied oil sample was diluted with deuterated chloroform. Field lock and shimming were achieved using the deuterium signal from CDCl_3 solvent.

^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded using 90° pulses with broadband proton decoupling (pulse program zgpg30); relaxation delay between consecutive accumulations were 3.3 s (and acquisition time was 2.3 s); spectrum width was set to 220.0 ppm; number of scans was 1300. Exponential digital filter with the LB parameter of 10 Hz was applied prior to Fourier transformation. Measurements were made at the temperature of 25°C . All the NMR spectra were integrated after baseline correction, and a mean of minimum three integration values has been taken for each calculation. The relative standard deviation of the results of manual integration did not exceed 3%.

3. Structural-group characterization and comparison of Norman 346, Norman 132 softeners and their synthetic plant Phytonorman 212, Phytonorman 213 analogues by high resolution ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy

The ^{13}C APT NMR spectra of Norman 346, Norman 132, Phytonorman 212, Phytonorman 213 softeners in deuteriochloroform with highlighting of the areas of hydrocarbon groups shown in the Figures 1-4. In these spectra the ^{13}C carbon atoms associated with an even and odd number of nearby protons are separated in phase by 180 degrees.

Fig. 1. ^{13}C APT NMR spectrum of Norman 346 softener in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 2. ^{13}C APT NMR spectrum of Norman 132 softener in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 3. ^{13}C APT NMR spectrum of Phytonorman 212 softener in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 4. ^{13}C APT NMR spectrum of Phytonorman 213 softener in CDCl_3 .

Figures 1-4 show the areas (shaded borders) of chemical shifts of the ^{13}C nuclei of studied oil samples: 170..180 ppm – carbon atoms of carboxyl groups (COOH); 140..160 ppm – tertiary carbon atoms of aromatic rings (C_{arH}) and quaternary carbon atoms (C), near N, O, S heteroatoms; 130..150 ppm – quaternary carbon atoms (C); 118..133 ppm – tertiary carbon atoms of aromatic rings (C_{arH}); 106..116 ppm - olefin fragments containing one C=C double bond; 22..75 ppm – methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) (upper signals) (secondary carbon atoms) and methine ($>\text{CH}-$) (lower signals) groups of alkyl substituents; 10..22 ppm - methyl (CH_3) groups or primary carbon atoms (in ^{13}C APT NMR spectrum they look like signals with negative phase).

Fractions can be described as the average ratio of structural groups (Table 1). Information obtained by integration of aromatic signals in individual spectral ranges is represented by the fraction of the corresponding carbon atoms relative to their total number. Fraction of aromatic carbons C_{ar} can be straightforwardly found from NMR spectra:

$$\text{C}_{\text{ar}} = \frac{I_{\text{ar}}}{\sum_j I_j}, \quad (1)$$

where C_{ar} is the fraction of aromatic carbons, I_{ar} is the total integral intensity of aromatic carbons, and I_j is the integral intensity of all functional groups in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the sample.

It is impossible to obtain unambiguous information on the content of hydrocarbons (alkanes, cyclanes) from ^{13}C NMR spectra, although this information is contained in the fragmentary composition, which can be determined with high accuracy. If integral

$$C_t = ((1.04I_t - 0.034I_{sq}) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (2)$$

$$C_p = ((1.02I_p - 0.006I_{sq}) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (3)$$

$$C_{sq} = ((1.04I_{sq} - 0.04I_t - 0.02I_p) / (I_t + I_{sq} + I_p))(1 - C_{ar}), \quad (4)$$

where C_t is the fraction of tertiary carbons; C_p , fraction of primary carbons; C_{sq} , fraction of secondary and quaternary carbons; I_t is the total integral intensity of tertiary (CH) groups; I_{sq} , total integral intensity of secondary (CH₂) and quaternary groups; I_p , total integral intensity of primary (CH₃) groups in ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the oil sample.

intensities of individual group signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum are known, then corresponding molar fractions of tertiary, primary, secondary and quaternary carbons can be calculated by the following formulas:

The molar fraction of aromatic carbons of ring groups ($C_{ar,ring}$) was calculated from the ratio of the integral intensity of resonant signals of protonated arenes (in the range of chemical shifts 118-133 ppm) divided by the total integrated intensity of all signals in the sample).

Table 1.

Molar fractions (%) of primary (C_p), secondary and quaternary (C_{sq}), tertiary (C_t), aromatic (C_{ar}) groups, aromatic carbons of ring groups ($C_{ar,ring}$) of Norman 346, Phytonorman 212, Norman 132, Phytonorman 213 softeners based on ^{13}C NMR spectra.

	Norman 346, %	Phytonorman 212, %	Norman 132, %	Phytonorman 213, %
C_p	9.0	10.2	12.5	10.0
C_{sq}	50.5	51.9	52.0	40.0
C_t	19.2	19.1	20.8	29.4
C_{ar}	21.2	18.8	14.7	20.6
$C_{ar,ring}$	11.4	13.7	5.8	15.2

Based on the obtained data obtained (Table 1) for Norman 346 softener and its synthetic plant analogue Phytonorman 212, no significant changes in the structural-group composition were observed, however, for Norman 132 softener and its synthetic plant analogue Phytonorman 213, a decrease in the concentration of secondary and quaternary hydrocarbon groups is observed by 12%, an increase in the concentration of tertiary and aromatic hydrocarbon groups by 8.6% and 5.9%, respectively. Phytonorman 213 softener also shows an almost threefold increase in ring aromatics compared to its non-synthetic counterpart - Norman 132.

Therefore, a study by high-resolution ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy can serve as one of the evidence for the effectiveness of the use of Phytonorman 213 synthetic plant softener compared to its non-synthetic counterpart Norman 132. This choice is also confirmed both in terms of environmental criteria and performance properties.

4. Conclusions

Molar fractions of major hydrocarbon groups and aromatic carbons of ring groups of Norman 346 and Norman 132 softeners and their synthetic plant analogues Phytonorman 212 and Phytonorman 213 were determined by ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy. The results of the study prove the effectiveness of the use of Phytonorman 213 plant synthetic softener compared to its non-synthetic counterpart Norman 132.

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